

AI-Enabled Real Time Object Detection and Classification for Retail Application

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Abstract: Real-time object detection and classification are critical in various industries, particularly in retail and manufacturing, where accurate product identification is essential. Traditional object detection techniques, such as Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG), Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) with Support Vector Machines (SVM), and deep learning models like Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD), require extensive feature extraction and computational resources for training. Implementing these computationally intensive models make them less efficient for large-scale, real-time applications. These challenges necessitate an automated approach that enhances accuracy, scalability, and speed while minimizing human intervention. In this article, we propose an approach for real-time object detection and classification using a robust deep learning model, YOLOv5, trained on the Groceries Dataset which contains 83699 images of 17 product categories, such as [milk, dessert, candy, chocolates, etc.], which has been under-sampled using random sampling technique to 20,294 images for Training, Validation and Testing phase. The YOLOv5 model processes real-time images and extracts features to classify the objects in the captured image. The proposed model undergoes training on the custom dataset and is evaluated on a test dataset to determine its accuracy in detecting and classifying objects. Later, to count number of objects we used defaultdict Datastructure to store the detected objects and compute the count of each class and displays the class – count pairs. The proposed network achieved an average accuracy of 88% after testing on the dataset.

Keywords –Object Detection, YOLOV5 (You Only Look Once), Spatial Pyramid Pooling fast (SPPF), Feature Extraction Network (FPN), Path Aggregation Network (PAN).

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Importance of AI in Object Detection

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has transformed object detection by enabling faster, more accurate, and scalable identification of objects across various industries. Traditional methods relied on manual feature extraction, environments. AI-driven deep learning models, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and YOLO (You Only Look Once), have automated feature extraction, allowing real-time processing with high precision. AI-powered object detection is widely used in retail, manufacturing, improving automation and decision-making. The ability to detect objects in real-time makes AI essential for applications like autonomous systems, quality control, and inventory management.

B. Challenges in Existing Methods

Traditional object detection methods, such as HOG-SVM and SIFT-SVM, rely on conventional feature extraction, making them inefficient for real-world applications due to their inability to handle objects in various conditions. While deep learning models like SSD have improved detection capabilities, they still face challenges, which limits real-time deployment, and a trade-off between speed and accuracy. These limitations emphasize the need for a fast, scalable, and efficient object detection system that ensures real-time performance without compromising accuracy.

C. Proposed Solution

To overcome these challenges, this paper presents an AI-enabled real-time object detection and classification system using YOLOv5, a deep learning-based model offers high-speed inference and accurate product recognition. Unlike traditional methods, YOLOv5 processes images in a single pass, significantly improving real-time performance. The proposed system is trained on a custom groceries dataset containing 83699 images, under-sampled to 0.25% across 17 product categories, enabling precise classification. The system provides real-time image processing and instant object detection and counting, making it ideal for automation in retail and manufacturing.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Object detection has evolved from traditional feature-based methods to modern deep learning-based techniques, enhancing accuracy and efficiency in real-time applications. Early approaches relied on handcrafted feature extraction methods such as Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) and Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT), combined with classifiers like Support Vector Machines (SVM), Decision Trees, and Random Forest. These methods, while effective in static environments, suffered from high computational costs, poor scalability, and challenges in handling variations in lighting, occlusion, and object orientation. To address these challenges, researchers have developed deep learning-based object detection models such as SSD and YOLO, which automate feature extraction and improve detection accuracy.

Darshan Yadav et al. [1] worked on real-time object detection using SSD MobileNet, leveraging deep learning for efficient object classification. Their approach involved image preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification, demonstrating an overall detection accuracy of 87%. However, the model faced challenges in small object detection and handling overlapping objects, which reduced its precision in complex environments.

Satya Prakash Singh et al. [2] explored YOLO-based object detection, integrating deep convolutional networks for high-speed, real-time classification. Their system processed images within video streams, effectively recognizing objects with improved accuracy. However, early YOLO versions struggled with localization errors, which affected the detection of small and densely packed objects, impacting its overall precision.

R. V. Iyer et al. [3] compared YOLOv3, YOLOv5s, and MobileNet-SSD V2 for real-time mask detection. YOLOv5s outperformed the others in both accuracy and speed, while MobileNet-SSD V2 was more lightweight but less effective with overlapping objects. The study highlights the balance between detection accuracy and computational efficiency in real-time applications.

A. M. Al-Sharman et al. [4] enhanced YOLOv5 for vehicle detection in UAV imagery, improving precision and recall, especially for small and dense objects. The model showed strong adaptability under diverse environmental conditions. This supports the use of customized YOLOv5 models for accurate, real-time object detection in complex scenarios like the one in this project.

These studies highlight the transition from feature-based methods to deep learning-driven object detection, demonstrating how SSD and YOLO architectures address real-time detection challenges while maintaining accuracy and computational efficiency.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology adopted in this study involves leveraging a pretrained YOLOv5 medium (YOLOv5m) model for object detection and classification. Instead of training the model from scratch, transfer learning is utilized by fine-tuning the pretrained model on our dataset. The methodology consists of two major stages: data preprocessing and model architecture exploration. The dataset is prepared and processed to align with the YOLOv5 framework, ensuring efficient learning and accurate predictions. Furthermore, YOLOv5m's multi-scale feature extraction, enhanced pooling mechanisms, and activation functions play a crucial role in refining the detection accuracy.

Fig 1 : Data Flow of Proposed System

Here goes the detailed analysis of each module:

1. Data Acquisition:

The dataset used in this study is the Groceries 83699 dataset, sourced from Roboflow Universe, specifically designed for object detection in retail products. This dataset consists of 17 distinct classes, including Alcohol, Candy, Canned Food, Chocolate, Dessert, Dried Food, Dried Fruit, Drink, Gum, Instant Drink, Instant Noodles, Milk, Personal Hygiene, Puffed Food, Seasoner, Stationery, and Tissue. The dataset comprises images labeled in YOLO format, where each annotation file includes bounding box coordinates (id, x_center, y_center, width, height). The images are divided into training, validation, and test sets, with 14,644 images for training, 4,089 for validation, and 2,091 for testing, ensuring a balanced distribution across classes with size 416×416 pixels.

Fig 2 : Input Sample Image.

1. Data Preprocessing:

Data Preprocessing enhances YOLOv5's detection accuracy by optimizing input images. The images are divided into training, validation, and test sets, with 14,644 images for training, 4,089 for validation, and 2,091 for testing, ensuring a balanced distribution across classes with size 416×416 pixels by using random under sampling technique. In the Inference stage, the process starts with image acquisition using OpenCV, followed by **letterbox resizing** to maintain aspect ratio while fitting the model's input size (640×640 pixels). The image is then converted from **BGR to RGB** and **normalized** to a [0,1] range for stable inference. To align with deep learning architectures, it is **transposed** and converted into a **PyTorch tensor** with dimensions [1, 3, H, W]. Padding is highlighted for debugging, ensuring spatial consistency. This structured pipeline improves real-time object detection efficiency while preserving image integrity the model's input requirements.

Fig 3 : Preprocessed Image.

2. Model Architecture Selection:

Selection architecture for our model plays a vital role. For our AI-enabled real-time object detection and classification project, we selected YOLOv5 due to its fast inference, high accuracy, and real-time adaptability.

YOLOv5 processes images in a single forward pass, making it efficient for real-time applications. It utilizes convolutional layers for feature extraction, SiLU activation for non-linearity,

and FPN-PAN networks for multi-scale feature representation. The model's anchor-based detection improves localization, while techniques like batch normalization and CSPDarknet backbone enhance performance. By fine-tuning a pretrained YOLOv5 model on our dataset, we achieved efficient object detection, classification, and counting, making it ideal for our application.

3. Model Building using YOLOv5M:

For our AI-enabled real-time object detection and classification project, we used the YOLOv5 Medium variant, a pretrained deep learning model optimized for both speed and accuracy. Instead of training a CNN from scratch, we leveraged transfer learning by fine-tuning the YOLOv5 model, which was originally trained on the COCO dataset, using our custom dataset. This approach allowed to achieve high accuracy while significantly reducing training time. The YOLOv5 architecture consists of multiple layers, each serving a specific role in detecting and classifying objects efficiently.

A. Importing library – “Pytorch”

PyTorch is a free and open-source deep learning framework developed by Facebook's AI Research Lab (FAIR). It is widely used for building and training deep learning models due to its dynamic computation graph and ease of use. PyTorch offers flexibility and scalability for tasks like image classification, natural language processing, and reinforcement learning. It provides strong GPU acceleration and an intuitive interface for research and production. The PyTorch library is imported using the command `import torch`.

B. Input Layer

Input Layer is the first Layer of CNN model. This layer serves as entry point for the dataset. The input layer is responsible for accepting images and preparing them for processing. The input image is first resized to 640×640 pixels while maintaining the aspect ratio through letterboxing, a technique that ensures consistent input dimensions without distortion. The image is then normalized and converted into a tensor for efficient deep-learning computations.

C. Convolutional Layer (CBL Blocks)

The backbone of YOLOv5 is built using CSPDarknet53 (Cross-Stage Partial Darknet53), which consists of multiple CBL blocks. Each CBL block is a combination of convolution (Conv2D), batch normalization (BN), and Leaky ReLU activation (L). The convolutional layers extract spatial features from the image, the batch normalization layer normalizes activations to stabilize training, and the Leaky ReLU activation function introduces non-linearity to capture complex patterns. The CSP (Cross-Stage Partial) connections improve feature propagation by splitting feature maps and merging them after transformation, reducing computational redundancy while preserving essential information.

A. Pooling layer (SPPF)

Pooling layer is responsible for decreasing the dimensions of feature maps. It extracts the important features from numerous features maps where it performs dimensionality reduction. The Spatial Pyramid Pooling Fast (SPPF) layer is included in the backbone to enhance the model’s ability to detect objects at different scales. It performs multi-scale feature extraction by applying multiple max-pooling operations with kernel sizes of 5×5, 9×9, and 13×13. This allows the network to retain critical spatial information while reducing the size of feature maps, ensuring better generalization for objects of varying sizes.

Fig 4: Max Pooling Operation

B. Feature Extraction (Neck : FPN , PAN)

The neck of YOLOv5 is designed to refine and aggregate features extracted by the backbone. It consists of a combination of Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) and Path Aggregation Network (PAN). The FPN helps retain multi-scale features by upsampling high-level feature maps and merging them with lower-level features, making small object detection more effective. The PAN further enhances this process by ensuring efficient information flow from both higher and lower layers, improving object localization and classification accuracy. Together, FPN and PAN strengthen the feature representation, ensuring robustness across various object sizes and orientations.

C. Fully Connected Layer

The head of the model is responsible for generating final object detections and classifications. It consists of multiple convolutional layers that refine feature maps before passing them through anchor-based detection mechanisms. Bounding boxes are predicted using regression techniques, and class scores are assigned to each detected object. The activation function used in this layer is the sigmoid activation function, which ensures that the predicted probabilities remain between 0 and 1. Finally, Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) is applied to remove overlapping bounding boxes and keep only the most confident detections.

D. ReLU -Activation Function

Activation functions play a crucial role in CNNs, including YOLOv5, by introducing non-linearity to capture complex patterns. YOLOv5 primarily uses the Leaky ReLU activation function, defined as $f(x) = x$ if $x > 0$, else αx , where α is a small constant (typically 0.01). Unlike ReLU, Leaky ReLU allows a

small gradient for negative inputs, preventing dead neurons and improving model learning.

Fig 5 : Leaky ReLU-activation function

The sigmoid activation function, defined as $f(x) = 1 / (1 + e^{-x})$, is used in the final detection layers to assign probability scores to each predicted object, aiding in classification and bounding box refinement.

Fig 6 : Sigmoid -activation function

H. YOLOv5 Architecture:

We have designed the YOLOv5 architecture in a way that follows a sequential process consisting of Convolutional Layers (CBL Blocks), CSP Bottleneck layers, Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP), and PANet Feature Fusion to extract and refine features efficiently. The model processes input images of 640 × 640 pixels and applies a combination of convolutional layers and CSP blocks to extract hierarchical features while maintaining high-speed processing. The architecture starts with an initial CBL Block (32 filters, 3 × 3 kernel), followed by another CBL Block (64 filters, 3 × 3 kernel) to refine low-level features. CSP Bottleneck layers with 128, 256, 512, and 1024 filters are integrated to enhance gradient flow and reduce computational redundancy. The Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) module further enriches the receptive field using multi-scale pooling operations (1 × 1, 5 × 5, 9 × 9, 13 × 13). For better feature representation, PANet Feature Fusion is applied, enabling bottom-up path augmentation to enhance small object detection. Additional CBL Blocks (256 and 128 filters) are used before passing the features to the detection layers. The detection head is divided into three layers to detect objects at multiple scales: small (80 × 80), medium (40 × 40), and large (20 × 20) objects. Finally, the output layer produces bounding boxes, class probabilities, and confidence scores, making YOLOv5 an efficient and robust real-time object detection framework.

Fig 7 : YOLOv5 Architecture

6. Model Execution:

This phase involves testing the trained YOLOv5 model for object detection in the Groceries dataset. After training and optimizing parameters, the model is deployed for inference. It processes new grocery images and predicts object locations, classifications, and confidence scores. During execution, the trained model analyzes input images by extracting features through CBL Blocks, CSP Bottlenecks, SPP, and PANet Feature Fusion. The detection layers generate bounding boxes for small, medium, and large objects. The output predictions are evaluated using metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and mAP (mean Average Precision) to assess model performance.

7. Model Testing and Evaluation:

When evaluating the effectiveness of the YOLOv5 model for grocery item detection, model testing plays a crucial role. This stage involves measuring precision, recall, F1-score and mAP (mean Average Precision) using the Groceries dataset. Preprocessing is performed on input images before they are fed into the trained model for prediction.

The evaluation process is conducted on the test images with the following metrics:

$$1. \text{ Precision (P)} = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$$

$$2. \text{ Recall (R)} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$$

$$3. \text{ Mean Average Precision (mAP)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum AP_i$$

8. Model Inference:

In the model inference phase, the trained YOLOv5 weights are used to detect and classify objects in new images. First, the input image undergoes preprocessing, where it is resized to 640 × 640, normalized, and converted into a tensor. This tensor is then sent to the YOLOv5 pipeline, which processes it through convolutional layers, CSP bottlenecks, and PANet feature fusion. After detection, post-processing techniques such as Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) filter out redundant bounding boxes. For object counting, a defaultdict is used to store the count of each detected object class. During inference, the model assigns class labels and updates the defaultdict for each detected object. Finally, the output image is displayed with detected objects, bounding boxes, confidence scores, and the total object count for each class.

IV SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system architecture follows a structured pipeline for real-time object detection and counting using YOLOv5. It starts with capturing raw image data from a camera or an uploaded image, which is then preprocessed through resizing, normalization, and format conversion. The preprocessed image is passed to the YOLOv5 model, which detects objects, assigns class labels, and generates bounding boxes with confidence scores. In the object identification phase, the detected objects are classified, and their counts are maintained using defaultdict(int), which allows efficient frequency tracking during inference. This ensures that objects are dynamically counted as they are detected. Additionally, a detected object log stores frequency data and allows cumulative analysis. Finally, the results are visualized and displayed to the user, with an annotated image highlighting the detected objects and their counts. This robust architecture ensures high efficiency and accuracy in applications like inventory management, and smart retail analytics.

Fig 8 : System Flow of Input.

V. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

A. Python

We developed this system using Python, leveraging libraries like NumPy, OpenCV, Torch, and YOLOv5 for image preprocessing, model training, and inference. Python's efficiency makes it ideal for deep learning and object detection.

B. Google Colab Notebook

We used Google Colab for model development and execution, enabling interactive coding, visualization, and seamless debugging in a development environment.

C. Flask

For web integration, we used Flask, allowing users to upload images, process them through the YOLOv5 pipeline, and display detected objects with their counts in real-time.

VI. RESULTS

We gained an average accuracy of 88% by training the model on Groceries dataset with 20 epochs. After training, weights file and other visualization graphs are generated.

The bar chart illustrates the distribution of instances across various product categories. "Tissue" exhibits the highest count, followed by "Drink" and "Dessert," while "Dried Fruit" has the lowest representation. This analysis provides insights into category prevalence within the dataset. Let know if you require further interpretation or modifications.

Fig 9 : Distribution of Product Categories by Instance Count

The **F1-Confidence Curve** shows the relationship between confidence scores and the F1-score for different object categories. A high F1-score at a lower confidence threshold indicates a well-performing model.

Fig 10 : F1-Confidence Curve for Object Detection Model

The **Recall-Confidence Curve** illustrates how recall varies with confidence levels across different object categories. Higher recall values at lower confidence thresholds suggest that most objects are being correctly identified.

Fig 11: Recall-Confidence Curve for Object Detection Model

In the Model Inference stage, the YOLOv5 model is loaded using `attempt_load(weights, device)`, where the trained weights file (`best.pt`) is used to perform object detection. The model runs in evaluation mode to ensure it processes images without modifying weights. The detection pipeline begins with the Preprocessing Stage, where the input image is read using `OpenCV (cv2.imread(image_path))`. To ensure the model processes images correctly, letterbox resizing is applied, which resizes the image to 640×640 pixels while maintaining its aspect ratio. The image is then converted from BGR to RGB, normalized to scale pixel values between 0 and 1, and transformed into a PyTorch tensor for model inference. If any padding is added during resizing, it is highlighted using a yellow border for visualization.

Once the image is preprocessed, it is passed through the YOLOv5 model for Object Detection. The model generates bounding box predictions, which contain object class labels, confidence scores, and bounding box coordinates. To refine these predictions, Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) is applied, filtering out overlapping detections based on confidence and IOU (Intersection over Union) thresholds. The detected bounding boxes, originally in the resized image format, are rescaled back to the original image dimensions using the `scale_coords` function, ensuring accurate positioning on the original image.

In the Postprocessing Stage, the detected objects are counted and labeled. The class names are retrieved, and a dictionary is used to count occurrences of each detected object using `defaultdict` datastructure. Bounding boxes are drawn around detected objects using `cv2.rectangle()`, and the corresponding class names with confidence scores are displayed using `cv2.putText()`. The final image, with bounding boxes and labels, is shown using `cv2.imshow()`, providing a visual representation of detected objects.

Detected Objects:
Puffed Food : 3
Dried Fruit : 2
Seasoner : 2
Canned Food : 1
Gum : 1

Fig 12: The Image with Detected Objects with Class-Count pairs.

VII. CONCLUSION

The primary objective of this study is to develop an AI-enabled real-time object detection and classification system using a custom Groceries dataset. By leveraging advanced deep learning techniques such as YOLOv5, the system accurately identifies and categorizes objects within images, ensuring high precision and efficiency. This research enhances the capabilities of computer vision, particularly in applications such as automated retail, smart inventory management, and intelligent surveillance. By improving real-time object detection and classification, this study contributes to technological advancements and provides a scalable, high-performance solution for practical implementations across various industries.

VIII. FUTURE SCOPE

The model can be enhanced to detect Overlapping objects even when they are stacked or placed closely together. It can further be enhanced to implement on videos

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